

TRIANGULAR MESHES: A SOLUTION TO RESIST TO GEOMETRIC DISTORTIONS BASED WATERMARK-REMOVAL SOFTWARES

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ABSTRACT

We present in this paper a compensation technique allowing to retrieve a watermark in an image attacked by random local geometric distortions, with the help of the original image, or its edges. For this purpose, we use a flexible triangular 2-D mesh, in order to compensate parts of geometric distortions that could be introduced by softwares such as Stirmark [12, 11]. In order to illustrate the usefulness of the compensation on attacked images, we use two watermarking techniques: a classical spread spectrum algorithm proposed by Cox et al. [3] (the watermark is embedded into a selected set of DCT coefficients) and a wavelet-based watermarking technique [4].

1 INTRODUCTION

Different researchers have already proposed watermarking methods, which are shown to be robust against arbitrary combinations of global image rotations, shifts and modifications of scale, for instance by making use of image or transform-based invariants [14], or grey-level histograms [2]. Others try to reverse the effect of geometric transforms by computing sliding local cross-correlations inside variable shaped blocks in the image [5], in order to re-synchronize the mark. Moreover, a registration known pattern can be introduced into the watermarked image, to cope with such geometrical attacks [10, 13]. Another solution consists in detecting invariant or interest points like corners, in order to use them as reference locations, to insert the watermark [1].

This paper investigates a non-blind method to reverse the effect of local geometric distortions, in order to recover the signature from an image close to the original one. Another non-blind method with the same objective has been introduced, making use of representative feature points at multiple resolutions [7].

2 DEFORMABLE TRIANGULAR MESHES

We propose to compensate geometric distortions with a triangular deformable mesh, and the original image, before to extract the watermark. For this purpose, we

compute a regular Delaunay triangulation on the watermarked attacked image, and we deform its structure, in order to map the texture of the attacked image onto the original one. The mapping is done by minimizing the overall mean square luminance matching error between the interior of corresponding triangles in the two images. Such principle is widely used for video compression by motion compensation with active meshes [16]. The image values or displacements of the interior pixels of a triangular block are related to those at nodal points, through an affine shape transformation of the triangle. The deformation of the mesh is done by associating one translation vector to each triangle vertices. Our objective is thus to find an approximation of an inverse geometric transform, based on local affine motion models, inside triangular blocks (figure 1).

Figure 1: (a,b): Illustration of the deformation of a regular triangulation in order to compensate local geometric distortions, by using affine piecewise transforms. Each node of the partition is translated, inside a polygon enclosed by its neighboring nodes (c), in order to minimize the mean square error between the original image, and the watermarked attacked image.

Figure 2 shows the effect of the geometric distortions compensation, using the original and attacked images. Figure 2.d shows the effect of the compensation, based on the thresholded highest gradient magnitudes of the two images: a large part of the deformations are compensated.

Figure 2: a: Absolute difference between the original image and the attacked watermarked image. b: Absolute difference between the original image and the attacked watermarked image after compensation of geometric distortions, with the help of the original image (d: with the help of the thresholded binary edges (c) of the original image).

3 AN ADAPTIVE RECTANGULAR PARTITIONING OF WAVELET COEFFICIENTS FOR IMAGE WATERMARKING

In order to test the distortions compensation algorithm, we introduce in this section a wavelet based watermarking method, which consists in thresholding and modifying the magnitude of wavelet coefficients [4]. Different other algorithms have been already proposed by researchers, for instance in [8, 15, 6, 17, 9], which are not directly based on a spread spectrum technique. We introduce here a new method which makes use of groups of significant coefficients, instead of isolated coefficients, in order to embed bits of the watermark.

3.1 Insertion of the watermark

The watermark is embedded into the three smallest detail subbands (LH, HH and HL) of an image, after computation of an adaptive rectangular partitioning of the significant wavelet coefficients (Figure 4). Each block of the partition is composed of approximately N significant coefficients, and each block is used to insert one bit of a watermark. The partition is computed, using

a *quatre-tree-like* procedure, by recursively splitting rectangular blocks in two sub-blocks with roughly the same number of coefficients.

Figure 3: Illustration of the watermarking algorithm: an adaptive spatial partition of the wavelet coefficients in the three lowest detail subbands is computed. The magnitudes of the coefficients in each block of the partition are then modified with reference to a uniform quantization scale and the value of the embedded bit.

Insertion of the watermark is done by modification of the magnitude of the wavelet coefficients, with reference to a uniform quantization scale. The scale is computed considering the minimum and maximum absolute values of the significant wavelet coefficients. The values of each coefficient in one block of the partition are then decreased or increased, depending on the bit 0 or 1 of the watermark, according to the quantization reference scale, as it is shown on figure 5. The resolution of such uniform scale, related to the number of decision levels, allows to control the visibility and the robustness of the watermark.

Figure 4: Partition of the 300 most significant of the 3072 coefficients in the three lowest subbands of the wavelet transform of image Lena 256×256 .

Let us note with E_j one of the k decision levels of the quantization scale, and C the magnitude of a significant wavelet coefficient. Let us suppose that $E_{j-1} < |C| < E_j$. The coefficient C is marked by increasing or decreasing its absolute value, compared to the middle value of the interval $[E_{j-1}, E_j]$. This interval is used to code one unique bit: 0 or 1. For instance, if $[E_{j-1}, E_j]$ is used to code a 1, if C has to be marked to 0, and if (see case 3 in Figure 6):

$$|C| \in \left[\frac{E_{j-1} + E_j}{2}, E_j \right] \text{ then } |C| = \frac{E_j + \frac{E_{j+1} + E_j}{2}}{2}.$$

Figure 5: Quantization scale and absolute values of the 300 original (a), and watermarked (b) significant wavelet coefficients in the three lowest subbands. The scale is composed of $k = 5$ intervals.

Figure 6: Watermarking of wavelet coefficients, depending on the uniform quantization scale. Dashed lines represent the middle of an interval $[E_j, E_{j+1}]$. Two consecutive intervals are used to code two different bits. The figure shows four different modifications of coefficients, depending on the bit to encode.

The watermarking depends on the quantization scale, computed from the value of the most and less significant wavelet coefficients. These two values will be let unchanged during the watermarking process, and coefficients under, but too close to the less significant value, will be decreased in order to preserve this supposed invariant feature. The number k of intervals of the quantization scale is a parameter accounting for watermark strength, and controls the visibility of the watermark (if k increases, the watermark strength is low, but the watermarking robustness decreases).

3.2 Extraction of the watermark

The (non-blind) extraction algorithm needs to reconstruct the adapted partition that was used by the watermarking algorithm (Figure 7). Thus, such partition has to be stored. The uniform quantization scale is computed, considering the most significant wavelet coefficients. Depending on image degradations, most of the high valued coefficients are preserved [4], except if the geometry

of the image is locally deformed, as it will be verified in section 4.

Figure 7: Extraction of the watermark, based on the adaptive partition of significant wavelet coefficients.

4 WATERMARK RETRIEVAL AFTER GEOMETRIC ATTACKS

We present in figure 8 watermark detection results, considering a non blind DCT-domain spread spectrum watermarking method initially proposed by I. Cox et al. [3].

Figure 8: Watermark detector response to 200 randomly generated watermarks, a: before any geometric attack and b: after geometric distortions introduced by Stirmark, on image Lena 256×256 . Detector response, after compensation of the geometric distortions, with the help of c: the original grey-level image, and d: the main binary edges of the original image.

The figure 8 shows the effect of the compensation of geometric distortions on image Lena 256×256 , by using a coarse triangulation, with equally spaced five lines, and five columns of triangle vertices. Such compensation is of course unable to reverse the same random geometric distortions introduced by Stirmark, but is sufficient to improve and make possible the watermark detection. Such result has been verified on different standard grey-level natural images.

	Reagan	Lena
Nb. of bits	34	33
Before comp.	50%	49%
After comp.	94.1%	94%

Figure 9: DWT-based watermarking of images Reagan and Lena 256×256 . The watermark can not be extracted from the watermarked images, attacked with geometric local distortions introduced by Stirmark. 94% of the bits of the watermark are extracted after compensation of the distortions.

Figure 9 confirms the usefulness of the compensation algorithm, even if the watermark is introduced on significant wavelet coefficients. Such compensation allows to reconstruct a good approximation of the relative magnitudes of the significant wavelet coefficients in the lowest subbands, which encode the low-pass features of the edged and textured regions of the image. Such result has been verified on different standard grey-level natural images.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a geometrical attacks compensation algorithm has been presented. We have shown that it allows to retrieve the watermark from an attacked image, if this one is watermarked in its DCT (spread spectrum technique) or its DWT (significant wavelet coefficients quantization) representations.

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